

QUALITY OF LIFE: AN EXPANDED AGENDA OF AIRPORT RESPONSIBILITY

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ABSTRACT:

This paper presents findings from the EU Horizon 2020 funded research project Aviation Noise Impact Management through Novel Approaches (ANIMA), which seeks to develop new methodologies, approaches and tools to managing aviation noise impact. Specifically, the work reported here sought to understand how airports can view their noise management efforts in the light of a wider responsibility for the quality of life (QoL) of local residents.

At the heart of the analysis is the acknowledgement that all businesses need a social licence to operate/grow, if their services are to be sustainable. In the case of airports, this means managing down potential negative impacts to socially acceptable levels, and also where possible contributing positively to the quality of life of local residents. If airports are to do this they need to understand the breadth of issues contributing to quality of life, indicators used to track performance, how current airport activities impact upon these QoL areas, and how that impact might be optimised.

Following a systematic review of attempts to capture and quantify indicators of QoL, this paper presents a range of quality of life “dimensions” and “topics” that airports can use to audit current activity, and thereby provides a rationale for strategic decisions on how best to use resources to optimise societal benefit.

The paper concludes by recognising that many airports engage in a range of activities that can have an impact on the QoL of local residents and indeed the wider population. However, these influences are often not reviewed as a coherent whole and thus their value is not optimised. It is proposed that a more systematic approach to the identification and

evaluation of current and future activity could inform more effective management of both the positive and negative impacts of airports on their local communities. It is recognised that every airport context is different and thus airports will need to work with their communities in defining their QoL priorities and thus the indicators that best address their needs.

1. INTRODUCTION

The impacts of airports and attendant activities on local communities and individuals have received limited attention. Government, local authorities and airport operators have tended to concentrate on positive impacts measured by contribution to gross domestic product (GDP), regional economies and international competitiveness, while negative impacts have been mainly related to noise and other environmental consequences.

However, with Quality of Life (QoL) receiving increased attention from academics, industry and the general public [1], a number of indices for overall QoL, happiness or wellbeing are now available, complemented by a vast array of indicators that address specific elements within the framework of QoL. Adopting a more wide-ranging assessment of the impact of an airport on its surrounding communities and individuals therein allows for a more balanced perspective of the full range of positive and negative consequences associated with an airport and aviation activity. Due regard for indicators for QoL could help airports and governance authorities to better measure impact, monitor progress and identify options for improvement.

This article draws on findings from a critical review to establish the relevant indicators on annoyance and residential QoL [2] and interviews with representatives of airports at the leading edge of engagement with QoL conducted for the larger

H2020 ANIMA project on aviation noise impact management through novel approaches. The article aims to provide new insights that could enable airports and authorities to move forward with their community strategies, by looking at domains that deal with quality of life and wellbeing, using insights into QoL and QoL indicators. It also aims to give airports and authorities the means to apply these concepts in their corporate and community strategies. Thus, it focuses on elements of QoL that are affected by aviation and/or that can be influenced by airports.

2. BACKGROUND

2.1 Defining Quality of Life

Quality of life has been variously described but, after reviewing a range of definitions (from WHO, EUROSTAT, the Dutch Social and Cultural Planning Agency and British Office for National Statistics), the following definition was adopted: 'the objective environmental parameters related to, and a person's subjective reflections on, current and future wellbeing'[2]. Given the concept's multi-faceted nature, QoL was further segmented into several dimensions to simplify its context and measurability by airports. As this process resulted in segmentation akin to that of EUROSTAT [1], the latter was adopted as the framework for the various dimensions of QoL included in the study. These are described in section 2.2.

2.2 Indicators of Quality of Life

For the collection of indicators, general indices for QoL, wellbeing and happiness from multiple global sources such as the WHO, EUROSTAT and the 'Happiness Report' by the Sustainable Development Solutions Network [3], as well as national sources from Germany, the UK, and The Netherlands were reviewed. Then, all indicators were mapped onto one of the QoL dimensions and assessed in terms of data availability, sensitivity to changes in QoL, general advantages, key limitations and relevance to an airport. It was considered vital that indicators were of good quality and could meet the goals of airport management. Thus, a selected indicator needed to be easily monitorable and, ideally, have associated high quality data available. To match airport operator aims, it was also important that the aspect captured by the indicator could be influenced by the airports. Figure 1 summarises the process of indicator

selection.

Figure 1: Process for selecting a suitable indicator [2]

This process resulted in nine dimensions being considered: health, economic and physical safety, natural and living environment, productive or main activity, education, material living conditions, leisure and social interactions, governance and basic rights, and overall life satisfaction. Further details about these indicators in relation to airports and their communities (the ANIMA set) are available in Appendix A.

2.3 Airports, noise and quality of life

Research suggests that the environment an individual lives in can affect subjective wellbeing [4] and that significant noise around people's dwellings leads to a reduction in health-related quality of life [5]. Researchers [6] state that attention has been given to the adverse impacts of transportation noise on health, quality of life and wellbeing (see, for example [7]). Aviation noise has been linked to stress, anxiety, hypertension, sleep and poor general health [8, 6 & 9] and dose-response relationships with residents' annoyance levels have been observed. Yet, [6] indicate that 'there is less evidence about the relationship between noise and measures of wellbeing such as life satisfaction, happiness, or feeling that one's life is worthwhile'.

In a study using the Mappiness iPhone app¹ to capture individuals' wellbeing scores around English airports in real-time, [10] found a 'negative association between aircraft noise, airport location, and subjective wellbeing.' The authors state that, while other studies based on cross-sectional data identified a negative association with life satisfaction

¹ This application was developed at the London School of Economics to capture and map happiness scores in the UK. (<http://v1.mappiness.org.uk>)

at the household level [6 & 11], their research provides greater robustness and higher levels of causal inference by controlling for a wider range of factors [12 & 13]. This provides important evidence of the negative externalities produced by the aviation industry, not only on those living in the local area, but also those within proximity to airports or aircraft noise [10].

A common objective QoL indicator in the aviation industry (and other industries) is the sound level. Sound levels can be used to assess the health impact of aircraft noise on the community. After establishing the noise contours, dose-response relationships can be used to derive estimated impact on the affected population measured for example in terms of 'people highly annoyed by noise' [14]. Although widely used, the correlation between sound levels and annoyance is debated, with concerns raised as to the appropriateness of universal dose-response relationship when airport context is so variable. Other acoustic indicators that might be appropriate for the estimation of noise annoyance could be the frequency of (high noise) events or the length and frequency of periods with low noise levels (respite).

A measure of noise annoyance is assessable via standardized single question items recommended by the International Organization for Standardization [15 & 16] with a numerical or verbal rating scale. As a high-level indicator health-related quality of life can be assessed by various standardized questionnaires (e.g. the short-form health survey questionnaire SF-36 or the WHOQoL developed by QoL-group of the WHO.) Both are rather long and as a consequence tend to be time-consuming and cost-intensive.

As is shown, noise and annoyance have traditionally been the focus of assessments of aspects of QoL around airports. However, there is growing evidence that other indicators of QoL may provide the potential for airports to do more for proximate communities, households and individuals. At the same time, there needs to be more work on noise and subjective wellbeing, health and quality of life.

3. AIRPORT INITIATIVES AND QUALITY OF LIFE

3.1 Assessing current activity

Findings of the review of indicators of quality of life, complemented by interviews with representatives of airports at the leading-edge of engagement with QoL – Amsterdam's Schiphol, London's Heathrow, Germany's Frankfurt and Romania's Iasi – are used to understand what airports are already doing with with regard to quality of life.

It was found that the airports participating in this element of the research were making considerable efforts with their communities but that communication and engagement strategies did not match their endeavours. Initiatives to address quality of life issues tended to be pursued in a haphazard manner: often in response to particular stimuli such as new infrastructure or political pressure. Engagement in quality of life factors was not systematic or strategy-based, often lacking an overall rationale. There was no cross-organisational approach to such engagement and any relevant activity was carried out independently by different parts of the airport company. There was seldom any evaluation of impact on specific quality of life topics nor on quality of life dimensions overall.

Nevertheless, airports recognise that there is a need to address QoL issues if the industry is to maintain/secure a 'licence to operate/grow' and further that more effective engagement with QoL issues may have a positive impact on those non-acoustic factors known to affect annoyance responses to noise [17]. Thus, a more systematic and critical approach to QoL may help mitigate noise impacts, as well as providing a framework for the evaluation of the efficacy of individual interventions.

3.2 Towards more systematic engagement

Given the desire to address quality of life issues, a more systematic approach to airport engagement is needed. We suggest that this process begins with an audit of engagement with QoL issues to:

- Determine which topics and dimensions are already being addressed
- Understand how specific interventions are being evaluated and whether a link to QoL outcomes can be made
- Identify topics/dimensions that are not being addressed, which the airport could/should be engaging with. These gaps could usefully form the basis of discussions with local communities as to what is seen to be most beneficial.

The audit would then form the basis for the development of a QoL strategy including elements such as defined activities, measurements and evaluation processes, and targets. This approach would allow airports to provide a rationale for why certain QoL dimensions and topics are being given precedence, whilst others may not be a priority (i.e. ones that airports could not reasonably influence). Thus, the audit framework would

- Build on existing strengths
- Address gaps in coverage

- Evaluate interventions based on indicators, which in turn can be assessed for their quality using the criteria: frequency, timeliness, breakdown by sub-categories and relevance (as defined in [1]).

The audit framework in Table 1 is an example of the type of tool which would allow airports to categorise their existing QoL interventions against a comprehensive list of QoL topics and dimensions.

Table 1 Possible Audit Framework

QoL Aspects		
Dimensions	Topics	Examples of Airport Actions/ Interventions
Health	Personal health	LAQ ² improvement campaigns, noise abatement
	Access to healthcare	-
Economic and physical safety	Economic safety	-
	Physical safety	Third-party risk control
Natural and living environment	Environmental conditions	LAQ monitoring Noise mitigation interventions Support for litter collection schemes
	Access to basic services, recreational/green areas	Investment in community sports facilities
	Access to basic services	Support for public transport services
Education	Educational attainment	Support for local schools
	Educational activity (formal and informal)	Staff volunteering in local educational institutions
	Population going on to tertiary education	Staff volunteering in local educational institutions
Main airport activities	Having a main activity	Hire locally
	Satisfaction	Offer on the job training, career opportunities
Material living conditions	Income	Sensible and transparent compensation for top management

	Material conditions	Insulation program to improve housing
Leisure and social relations	Availability	Sponsorship for local community groups
	Quality	-
	Access	-
Governance and basic rights	Attitude	Fair and transparent procedures
	Equality	-
	Active citizenship	-
Overall QoL	Life satisfaction	-
	Affects	-
	Purpose	-

NB Airport interventions listed here are for illustrative purposes only (i.e. they are not intended to be representative nor recommended).

4. CONCLUSIONS

As we explore the negative consequences of airport development and activity, one of the detrimental health outcomes requires direct address: the impact on quality of life. To achieve insights into QoL factors amongst nearby communities and individuals, airports can benefit from looking at local needs and daily lives as they shape individual lived experience and colour community views. Within this context, it is also important to consider consequences of airport activity and their contribution to quality of life more broadly, positive and negative, particularly if a negative impact is irreducible, pointing to a need to explore quality of life to help counter annoyance and other associated health impacts to see if airports can negotiate a better offer for communities (i.e. one that offsets any acknowledged negative impacts with positive change for communities designed to improve quality of life).

The indicators identified in this work can be used by airports to monitor and improve the nine dimensions of Quality of Life. In some areas information/data on high quality indicators are readily available. When the required data is not available or not available for the right population, established questionnaires can be used to fill these gaps. The selection of priorities of dimensions might be highly dependent on existing local and/or cultural factors that influence how communities value different dimensions in different ways, for example, the existing baseline impacts, the perceived improvement or reduction of QoL as a result of airport operations can differ significantly from location to location. Thus at the heart of addressing QoL effectively is the need for dialogue with communities over how best to optimise key features that impact on the day-to-day lives of

² LAQ = Local Air Quality

residents.

It is important to remember that some changes may have re-distribution effects and thus there may be advantages for some and disadvantages for others. Assuming the airport is already within legal limits, the audit framework can be used to review existing measures in a single coherent overview. In a cooperative approach the airport and the community could identify priorities among the dimensions, select the indicators for tracking performance and set goals to strive for.

Together, airport and community can use the concept of QoL, the indicators and the audit framework to improve airport-community relations and engagement and enable more effective interventions that provide real benefit to those living near an airport.

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6. APPENDIX A: INDICATORS OF QoL – THE ANIMA SET

A1.0 Indicators of Health

In this context, health divides into the topics of 'outcome' (including self-perceived health and health effects), determinants of health and access to healthcare. Outcomes take account of the health status of individuals including physical and mental health. For the topic, healthcare, the availability and accessibility as well as the quality of medical care are the focus. Personal health determinants like physical activity, diet, tobacco consumption and alcohol consumption are considered due to their influence on overall health. External stimuli such as noise and air quality also influence health.

Indicators differ in their method of assessment, their level of detail and their scope. Subjective and objective measurements mainly differ in methods of assessment. While objective measures are measured or observed from a third party (e.g. % of cancer patients) and are often derived from public data, subjective data is gathered via one's own rating of a situation or subject (e.g. self-perceived health status). Furthermore, there are high-level indicators (e.g. life expectancy) and more specific indicators that address a specific part of a topic (e.g. sleep quality as part of overall health). Finally, the perspective of an indicator can be at community level (e.g. infant mortality in a country) or on an individual level. The classification of indicators into the types described above is not always straightforward and it should be recognised that there can be overlap as the categories are not necessarily mutually exclusive.

For the selection of appropriate health indicators, the relevance for airport use must be considered. It is important that a chosen indicator can be influenced and addressed by an airport, its stakeholders and interventions. Data availability and an ability to measure changes in the indicator are also required.

A2.0 Indicators of economic and physical safety

This dimension encompasses measures of economic stability and safety from physical harm. These indicators are less about the level of income and material living conditions and more about resilience, financial and physical stability and a positive outlook on these variables in the future. Economic and physical safety can come from one's own means or from friends, family or the government.

EUROSTAT (2015a) identifies subjective high-level indicators for economic safety such as the binary response to the question: "Are you able to cope with unexpected financial expenses?". Other subjective indicators are the binary responses to questions such as "Do you have someone to count on in times

need?" (SCP, 2017) and "Do you have someone for support?" (Helliwell, Layard, & Sachs, 2017). These indicators measure resilience and possible sources of economic security at an individual level.

In addition, several objective indicators can be used to measure enablers of economic safety. Relevant examples are job security (type of contract), minimum wage (at a national level) and the availability of social security (as part of the job benefits or at a national level) (SCP, 2017). These indicators can be measured at both community and individual level.

With respect to physical safety, EUROSTAT distinguishes between acts of crime, the perception of crime and the perception of physical safety. Objective indicators for the prevalence of crime are reported crime rates [for example, sources such as the Crime Survey for England and Wales and police crime data (ONS UK, 2018)]. Reported crime does not always match with the perception of crime. Therefore, it is useful to include indicators on perceived safety. Subjective indicators are responses to questions like "Do you ever feel unsafe in your own neighbourhood?", "Do you regularly feel unsafe in your own neighbourhood?", "Do you ever feel unsafe in general?" (CBS, 2017).

For airports, the use of indicators to monitor economic and physical safety of their community can help highlight where interventions can be focused, within their span of control, to make a real difference for individuals and community.

A3.0 Indicators for natural and living environment

This dimension refers to environmental aspects of quality of life. It focuses both on perceived environmental influences and perception of the environmental surroundings, as well as objectively measured appearance of green and/or recreational areas close to the place of residence, surrounding environment in general and environmental pollution. According to EUROSTAT (2015a), "*Environmental conditions affect human health and well-being both directly and indirectly, while residents value their rights to access environmental resources. Moreover, environmental factors indirectly affect other quality of life aspects, including economic prosperity and inequality, e.g. by directly affecting property prices and housing conditions.*"

An objectively measured indicator is population or housing density in an area whereas a subjectively examined indicator in this dimension is self-reported exposure to any kind of pollution or grime, and the perception of environmental problems.

Aircraft noise is already within the focus of many airports. On a community level, another objectively measured indicator is traffic noise exposure. In

many countries, there are noise maps that are created for the purpose of documentation and monitoring of regulatory limits. EU countries are obliged to make strategic noise maps following the Environmental Noise Directive, (Directive 2002/49/EC). In return, self-perceived exposure to noise is an evaluation on an individual level. The EUROSTAT set identifies explicit indicators referring to noise: 'noise from neighbours' and 'noise from the street', which are described as 'noise from neighbouring apartments, staircase or water pipe' and "noise linked to traffic (street or road, plane, railway), linked to business, factories, agricultural activities, clubs and yard' (EUROSTAT, 2015b). In addition, on both a more specific and individual level, perceived residential satisfaction is an appropriate indicator to provide information about specific qualities of the residential area of interest, for example, measured with the 16-item questionnaire 'satisfaction with residential quality' by Wirth (2004).

Indicators of natural and living environment can be directly addressed by airport interventions. *Perception of the surrounding environment is influenced by nearby airports and associated infrastructure. Further, built landscape and environmental pollution is often directly linked to airports, thus interventions can target environmental pollution such as noise exposure. Other interventions such as appropriate communication campaigns can be used to emphasise the positive influence of airports on the surrounding environment.*

A4.0 Indicators for work or other main activity
A main activity refers to a person's paid or unpaid work and can be split into having a main activity and qualitative aspects of that main activity. Having a main activity is very important for quality of life. Several objective indicators are available. A common indicator is the unemployment rate. The unemployment rate is the number of people without work as a percentage of the labour force³. Another objective indicator is the percentage of people aged 15/16 to 74 not in employment, education or training. The former excludes students and people not looking for work, the latter does not (ONS UK, n.d.).

Qualitative indicators relate to work-life balance and job satisfaction. A quantitative indicator for the work life balance is the number of hours worked. According to the third European QoL survey, wellbeing improves with the number of hours worked up to 41 hours per week (Eurofound, 2013). Job satisfaction can be measured with a subjective questionnaire with a Likert-scale. For example "How satisfied are you with your job?".

³ all aged between 15/16 and 74 who are willing and able to work within two weeks (EUROSTAT, 2010)

Airports are often major generators of job opportunities. This happens directly via jobs with the airport operator, airlines, air traffic control, ground handling agents and via airport suppliers and induced economic activity (for example, international trade and business, tourism).

A5.0 Indicators for education

Education is another pillar of QoL as it raises a person's potential. Moreover, education increases the chances of a meaningful and well-paid job that increases the standard of living. As such, it has a positive impact on a person's future outlook. In addition, education appears to have a positive impact on health, with higher reported happiness and fewer mental illnesses associated with higher levels of educational attainment (EUROSTAT, n.d.).

A common objective indicator is the expected and mean years of schooling for a community as tracked by UNESCO (UNDP, 2016). Another objective indicator is the percentage of people aged 15 to 74 without any formal qualifications (ONS UK, n.d.). The indicator 'percentage of people aged 15/16 to 74 not in employment, education or training' also applies to education.

Airports can improve the level of education in their community through their offer (for example, of educational packages and internship opportunities to students and computer training for seniors). In addition, on-the-job training opportunities provide life-long learning for the airport's workforce.

A6.0 Indicators for material living conditions

This dimension is related to economic safety and main activity but deals with a person's possessions and consumer power. It can be divided into income and material conditions.

'Income' covers income levels, poverty, and the distribution of wealth. An objective indicator is the natural log value of the income capped at an annual income of US\$70,000. The rationale behind using a logarithmic scale is that the impact of additional income on quality of life diminishes as the income becomes higher. At approximately \$70,000 (exact amount differs per region), additional income cannot be correlated to increased QoL (UNDP, 2016). Poverty can be measured by the percentage of households with an income below 60% of the median income (ONS UK, n.d.). Distribution of income can be expressed using the Gini-index. A (theoretical) Gini value of 0 indicates that all households earn an equal amount, whereas a (theoretical) value of 1 indicates that all income is earned by just one household. The optimal Gini value is a highly contested. Income inequality can stimulate entrepreneurship and incentives to do

better.

However, extreme inequality can lead to a low satisfaction among those worse off.

'Material conditions' can refer to material deprivation and housing conditions. An important example index for material conditions is the Dutch 'Life situation index', an aggregated index on housing and having certain items such as a television, computer, ... (SCP, 2010). The index can be augmented with questionnaires on the content with the material conditions.

As a job provider, airports have a direct impact on income. Other elements of income are harder to influence. However, if individual income distribution in nearby communities is seen by residents to be an issue, an intervention that encourages and supports new social enterprise development may be appropriate and would illustrate corporate social responsibility on the airport's part. To improve material conditions, airports may draw on a suite of options such as insulation programmes (as many do already), providing access to computers in deprived communities or funding training programmes for job-seekers.

A7.0 Indicators for leisure and social interactions
This dimension includes the leisure and social interactions. Subtopics of leisure are quantity, quality and access to leisure in terms of availability of time to do things people enjoy and participation in chosen leisure activities. Subtopics of social interactions are activities with, and for, people which help develop supportive relationships and social cohesion.

Leisure and social interactions can also be observed at a community and an individual level. As an indicator at a community level, the percentage of people engaging in voluntary work could be useful, whereas satisfaction with the voluntary assignment represents leisure on an individual level.

Referring to the ANIMA-set of indicators, the UK's Office for National Statistics (ONS), for instance, identifies in the assessment of National Wellbeing subjective measurements for leisure in the form of single-item-measurements. Satisfaction with amount of leisure time is assessed using a 7-point Likert scale with responses ranging from "Completely dissatisfied" to "Completely satisfied" (ONS, 2017). Engagement in voluntary work is examined with the question 'How frequently do you do unpaid voluntary work?', again responses are collected on a 5-point-likert scale from 'at least once a week' to 'never/almost never' (ONS, 2017), whereas objectively measured engagement in voluntary work could derive from national public data.

For the subtopic social interactions, there are mainly

subjective indicators that refer to social interactions both at a community and individual level. These are supplemented by high-level and specific indicators such as the overall satisfaction with personal relationships or frequency of getting together with relatives (EUROSTAT, 2015a). The ANIMA set contains further examples in the field of social interactions from the ONS and the Dutch 'Life situation index'. Supportive relations can be investigated by asking whether respondents have someone to rely on (in case of serious problems), using questions like "How much can you rely on your spouse/family member/friend if you have a serious problem?" with responses categorised using a 5-point Likert scale from 'a lot' to 'no friends, family or spouse' (ONS, 2017). Similar items are included in the 'Life situation index' with questions about social isolation, including items that focus on having someone to communicate with or having someone to turn to (SCP, 2010).

Airports can address this dimension by offering participative events aimed at encouraging social interaction. Such events and activities can have the positive side effect of residents becoming acquainted with the neighbouring airport and its employees. Some examples of interaction opportunities are open days for residents in general, schools and kindergartens, the hosting of leisure and sports competitions and sponsoring sportswear for local clubs. Airport charity foundations can also support local people and communities. By capturing stories from local residents about the ways in which the airport contributes to their holiday-making, leisure and social interactions by enabling access to distant destinations, building connectivity to visit loved ones and acting as a socially responsible neighbour can provide opportunities for quality messaging about the operator.

A8.0 Indicators for governance and basis rights
This dimension captures attitudes towards institutions and public services, aspects related to discrimination and equal opportunities as well as active citizenship. Subtopics for institutions and services, for instance, refer to trust and/or satisfaction in institutions and trust and/or satisfaction in public services.

Based on the ANIMA-set of indicators, the assessment of the UK's ONS on national wellbeing offers indicators in the segment government via an objective and a subjective measure: voter turnout and trust in government. Voter turnout is an objective high-level measure that reflects a direct active civil participation in political process. Comparison is possible over time and region, thus, it is usable at a community level. Trust in government, however, is a subjective indicator and is assessed by the ONS by asking about the tendency to trust a range of institutions (ONS,

2017).

Trust can, therefore, be measured at a community and individual level.

Focusing on basic rights, EUROSTAT provides an objective high-level indicator referring to equality in form of gender pay gap using statistical data (EUROSTAT, 2017). Other examples for objectively measured indicators for equality are indicators that have influence in the Gender Equality Index (European Institute for Gender Equality, 2017) such as power in the form of gender distribution in share of ministers.

Some indicators in this dimension may be difficult to address or, indeed, not applicable in the context of airports, since the influence of operators and interventions in this field tends to be small and may be inappropriate. Thus, criteria for relevance need to be aimed at capacity to influence QoL. Nevertheless, airports adopting transparent procedures and governance can lead by example.

A9.0 Indicators for overall quality of life

This dimension contains the subjective rating of quality of life for three aspects: life satisfaction, affects (presence of positive feelings and absence of negative affects) and meaning and purpose of one's life.

Various national and international initiatives have developed their own approaches to measure quality of life, in general, addressing multiple topics (including the OECD with its Better Life Index, the Dutch 'Life situation index' or UK's Office for National Statistics with its Measuring National Well-being programme) that all cover relevant topics of quality of life (and often overlap in terms of addressed topics). In various approaches and initiatives examined, no summaries or aggregation of the indicators to one global indicator are carried out but, rather, subtopic indicators are summed up.

Subjective measures are the rating of overall life satisfaction (Eurofound, 2012), similarly assessed by the ONS asking participants to rate their satisfaction with their lives overall on a scale of 0 to 10 (with 0 'not at all' to 10, 'completely') or the Personal wellbeing index (The International Well-being Group, 2006) comprising eight items to rate satisfaction in eight different life domains.

Criteria of relevance to airports in this indicator are capacity to influence and scale of influence.